

BBO tuned PI controller for the stability of TCP networks

Manal Hadi Jaber¹, Manal Kadhim Oudah¹, Mohammed Qasim Sulttan¹, Salam Waley Shneen²

¹Electromechanical Engineering Department, University of Technology-Iraq, Baghdad, Iraq

²Nanotechnology and advanced material research Center, University of Technology-Iraq, Baghdad, Iraq

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ABSTRACT

The congestion is the most important issue that effects on the performance of data transition over internet networks. One of the important techniques developed is active queue management (AQM) that prepares an efficient congestion control by reducing losing packets, queue size, and energy consumption. Therefore, AQM technique deemed as a base of many congestion control algorithms schemes. This work suggested the using of proportional integral (PI) controller as an AQM and then use an optimized control system such as biogeography-based optimization (BBO) with PI controller as (BBO-PI). The optimal control (BBO-PI) is characterized by access to design and fine-tuning of defining the shapes of the optimal parameters of PI controller. The BBO algorithm was implemented by using the mathematical system model by M-file/Matlab and Simulink. The simulation results showed the best performance for the transmission control protocol (TCP) network when compared the system with using the PI controller and using optimal control (BBO-PI), the ratio of enhancing the system with using of BBO-PI better than using a PI controller only in terms of rising time is 1.11, settling time is 2.85 and overshooting is 85%. Therefore, the proposed method was very fast and required few iterations.

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Corresponding Author:

Mohammed Qasim Sulttan

Electromechanical Engineering Department, University of Technology-Iraq

Baghdad, Iraq

Email: mohammed.q.mohammed@uotechnology.edu.iq

1. INTRODUCTION

In internet services, applications and quality of service (QoS) [1] the standard communication protocols such as transmission control protocol (TCP) is the most widely used, therefore, the success of the internet depends on the best design of TCP, but the TCP still represent the bottleneck in throughput of internet network, due to large latency of the network, packet losses in-network, and delay time in-network. So with those problems there in wireless links (Wi-Fi, LTE, 3G, WiMAX) [2]-[5], the TCP tends to send with low rate than the network design allows. Today TCP is considered one of the substantial protocols of the internet protocol (IP) [6], [7] set, it guarantees the error-checked, well-ordered, during movement the packets of information among networks. TCP is accountable for rearrangement the received packets and delivering it to its destination without data gaps or errors [8], [9].

TCP includes other essential functions such as controlling congestion on the internet network and ensuring that the receiver doesn't get inundated with much data (flow control). Both congestion control and flow control need a form of the transmission rate conditioning based on feedback from the receiver [10], [11]. Therefore, in this work, we focused on both congestion control and flow control by optimizing the controlling approaches them. The optimizing TCP [12], [13] is achieving by controlling some available parameters and this leads to improvement of the total performance of the protocol. TCP performance measure

in generally by using a few key metrics, such as delivery speed (bit/sec) and retransmission the data that represent repeated data send on the network [14], [15].

Many studies took up to improve the performance of TCP network, used some optimization techniques such as genetic algorithm (GA) [16], [17], fuzzy logic (FL) [18], [19], and particle swarm optimization (PSO) [20], [21]. With traditional control techniques such as proportional integral derivative (PID) [22], [23], proportional integral (PI) [24], or proportional derivative (PD) [25]. Biogeography-based optimization (BBO) [26], [27] is one of the important optimization techniques which depended in this paper, it has important features will mention later.

In 2008 and from biogeography inspired, Ma and Simon [28] advanced a new algorithm known BBO. It can be used for a natural process also can be modelled it to reach to optimization approach. BBO is one of the modern intelligence techniques that are used to improve the functioning of systems due to the ability to tune the parameters in varied applications. Sheikhan *et al.* [29] used two (ANN)-based controller techniques to adaptive the queue in TCP networks, the proposed controllers include two optimization algorithms GA and PSO, it depends on radial bias function (RBF) with an error-integral term to robust the work of RBF, the results showed the effectiveness of proposed controllers in issues of packet loss and outperforms drop tail. Sabry and Kaittan [30] suggest used grey wolf optimizer (GWO) algorithm with a fuzzy-PI controller as an active queue management (AQM) for controls congestion in internet routers and for fulfilling faster response and reduce the steady-state error, the simulation results showed good stability for the proposed controller with the ability to reach a fast response with different loads for the network. Fajri and Ramli [31] are proposed to use a nelder-mead simplex (NMS) method to get the best parameters of the PID controller to enhance the work of TCP/AQM router system, the results of this work appeared the effectiveness of combination between NMS and integral of time-weighted absolute error (ITAE) criterion on other criteria in sense of control for congestion in a network. Li *et al.* [32] are considered a novel AQM scheme for TCP network, when they using integral back-stepping technique (IB) and minimax method with a suitable condition and conformable control, the simulation results showed are not only used to deal with perturbations produced by user datagram protocol (UDP) streams but the convergent time of the signals can also be shortened. Wang *et al.* [33] proposed an approach consist of the backstepping-like procedure and fuzzy approximation manner to satisfying the values of the transient and steady-state error. The results state the effectiveness of the proposed approach when analysis for stability showed that all signals within the closed-loop are uniform, semi-global and bounded.

This work proposes using a proportional integrity controller (PI) with the BBO algorithm as an AQM for internet routers in TCP networks. The optimization method BBO was used in this work to tune the PI controller parameters to reach closely an optimal performance of the PI controller to reduce the effect of congestion in TCP networks. The work goes toward fulfilling a stable queue length, improve latency to prevent TCP failure or slowing down.

The remainder of this paper is organized as: section 2, include the simulation model for TCP/AQM system with BBO-PI. The simulation results wrote down in section 3. The conclusion of this paper is in section 4.

2. SIMULATION MODEL FOR TCP/AQM SYSTEM WITH BBO-PI

The system of TCP/AQM that depended in this work shown in Figure 1. The system includes routers, sources, and standardized control networks. Table 1 shows the parameter values of the TCP/AQM system and the (1)-(5) represent the mathematical design of the TCP/AQM system.

Figure 1. The TCP/AQM network topology

Table 1. Parameter values of the TCP/AQM system

The promulgation delay	Link capacity	TCP session number	Packet size	Maximum queue length in router 1	The desired queue size	The round-trip time
$T_p = 0.2$ seconds	3750 packet/secs $C = 15$ Mbps	$N = 60$	500 byte	$q_{max} = 700$ packets	$q_{des} = 300$ packets	$R = 0.253$ seconds

$$\dot{w}(t) = \frac{1}{\frac{q(t)}{C} + T_p} - \frac{w(t)}{2} \frac{w(t-R(t))}{\frac{q(t-R(t))}{C} + T_p} p(t-R(t)) \tag{1}$$

$$\dot{q}(t) = \begin{cases} -C + \frac{N(t)}{\frac{q(t)}{C} + T_p} w(t) & \text{if } q(t) > 0 \\ \max \left\{ 0, -C + \frac{N(t)}{\frac{q(t)}{C} + T_p} w(t) \right\} & \text{if } q(t) = 0 \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

$$T.F = \frac{122.8s^3 + 3299s^2 + 2455s + 3.252e^{04}}{s^4 + 1.136s^3 + 20.14s^2 + 11.26s + 99.8} \tag{3}$$

$$F(s) = \frac{q(s)}{p(s)} = \frac{\frac{C^2}{2N} e^{-sR}}{(s + \frac{2N}{R^2 C})(s + \frac{1}{R})} \tag{4}$$

$$\text{sat}(p(t-R(t))) = \begin{cases} 1, & p(t-R(t)) \geq 1 \\ p(t-R(t)), & 0 \leq p(t-R(t)) < 1 \\ 0, & p(t-R(t)) < 0 \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

Where \dot{w} and \dot{q} is the time-derivative of w and q respectively. W = rate of TCP window size, R = measured in seconds, $R = \frac{q}{C} + T_p$, q = rate of queue length, C = capacity of the link, N = session number, T_p = promulgation delay, p = packet sign probability. Figure 2 shown the controller model for TCP/AQM system and Figure 3 depicted the block diagram of TCP/AQM System. The PI controller used as an AQM to control congestion in TCP networks, the (6) clarify the factors and constant gain parameters of the PI controller. Figure 4 shows the Simulink model of the PI controller (AQM) for TCP network.

$$s(t) = K_p e(t) + K_I \int_0^t e(t) dt \tag{6}$$

Where: $e(t)$ = the error signal between (the input reference and the process output), $ec(t)$ = the change of error signal, K_p = proportional constant gain, and K_I = integral constant gain.

Figure 2. Schematic model of a controller with a TCP network

Figure 3. System block diagram of TCP/AQM network

Figure 4. Simulink model of PI for TCP network

The performance of the PI controller as an AQM is not enough for TCP networks, so it needs optimization technique such as BBO to improve its work. BBO tune the parameters of the PI controller to reach the best performance for TCP/AQM system. Figure 5 shows the Simulink model of BBO-PI for TCP/AQM system. The BBO is a heuristic algorithm recently developed, its working principle is based on the mathematical study of biogeography, it was shown an impressive performance on numerous known benchmarks [34]. Such as many evolutionary algorithms, BBO works on the principle of probability, the probability of an individual participating in an advantage with the rest of the population is proportional to his fitness. The probability of an individual acquiring a trait from the rest of the population decreases with fitness, for more details about BBO see [35]-[38].

Figure 5. Simulink model of BBO-PI for TCP network

3. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation model of this work is shown in Figure 6, the figure exhibits the model details which contain the TCP/AQM network with two types of controllers: 1- PI and 2- BBO-PI. The simulation results presented in Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 9. Figure 7 show the performance curve for the TCP/AQM network with PI controller. Figure 8 show the performance curve for the TCP/AQM network with BBO-PI controller and Figure 9 exhibit the performance curve for the TCP/AQM network with both PI and BBO-PI controller to make a comparison between them. Table 2 appears the comparison between the performance of TCP/AQM network when using a PI controller and using BBO-PI controller. From Table 2 can see the difference in the results for rising time, settling time and overshooting percentage. Leads to a difference in the performance of TCP/AQM network, the performance of TCP/AQM network with BBO-PI controller is better than the performance with PI controller. The TCP/AQM network is more stability when using BBO-PI controller than using a PI controller.

Table 2. The result values to compare the TCP/AQM network performance with BBO-PI and PI controller

System response parameters	PI controller	BBO-PI controller
Rising time	0.05	0.045
Settling time	0.2	0.07
Overshooting	25.2 %	0.3 %

Figure 6. Simulation model for BBO-PI and PI controller of TCP network

Figure 7. Simulation results for PI controller of TCP network

Figure 8. Simulation results for BBO-PI controller of TCP network

Figure 9. Simulation results for PI and BBO-PI controller of TCP network

4. CONCLUSION

The optimization of TCP based network applications and services performance by using one of the modern intelligence techniques became distinctly matter upon the quality of internet networks by speeding throughput, using large capacities, reducing retransmission rates, and decreasing the latency in the network. Also, an optimization solution for TCP leads to two important results, treating the issue of packet loss in last-mile networks, treating congestion in last-mile networks and decreasing the period of arriving at available bandwidth. The performance of the network has been improved through the use of BBO-IP controller, and this was evident through the simulation results.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Karakus and A. Durrresi, "Quality of service (QoS) in software defined networking (SDN): A survey," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 80, pp. 200-218, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jnca.2016.12.019.
- [2] O. Lamrabet, N. El Fezazi, F. El Haoussi, E. H. Tissir, and T. Alvarez, "Congestion Control in TCP/IP Routers Based on Sampled-Data Systems Theory," *Journal of Control, Automation and Electrical Systems*, vol. 31, pp. 588-596, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s40313-020-00582-z.
- [3] L. Ma, X. Liu, H. Wang, and Y. Zhou, "Congestion Tracking Control for Wireless TCP/AQM Network Based on Adaptive Integral Backstepping," *International Journal of Control, Automation and Systems*, vol. 18, pp. 2289-2296, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s12555-019-0724-y.
- [4] C. Deng *et al.*, "IEEE 802.11 be Wi-Fi 7: New challenges and opportunities," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 2136-2166, 2020, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2020.3012715.
- [5] A. Bhattacharya, B. Roy, S. K. Chowdhury, and A. K. Bhattacharjee, "An isolation enhanced, printed, low-profile UWB-MIMO antenna with unique dual band-notching features for WLAN and WiMAX," *IETE Journal of Research*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 496-503, 2022, doi: 10.1080/03772063.2019.1612284.
- [6] R. Ritchey, B. O'Berry, and S. Noel, "Representing TCP/IP connectivity for topological analysis of network security," in *18th Annual Computer Security Applications Conference, 2002. Proceedings.*, 2002, pp. 25-31, doi: 10.1109/CSAC.2002.1176275.
- [7] A. Afanasyev, J. Burke, T. Refaei, L. Wang, B. Zhang, and L. Zhang, "A brief introduction to Named Data Networking," in *MILCOM 2018 - 2018 IEEE Military Communications Conference (MILCOM)*, 2018, doi: 10.1109/MILCOM.2018.8599682.
- [8] G. Chuanxiong and Z. Shaoren, "Analysis and evaluation of the TCP/IP protocol stack of LINUX," in *WCC 2000 - ICCT 2000. 2000 International Conference on Communication Technology Proceedings (Cat. No.00EX420)*, 2000, vol. 1, pp. 444-453, doi: 10.1109/icct.2000.889245.
- [9] M. K. Debnath, T. Jena, and S. K. Sanyal, "Frequency control analysis with PID-fuzzy-PID hybrid controller tuned by modified GWO technique," *International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems*, vol. 29, no. 10, 2019, doi: 10.1002/2050-7038.12074.
- [10] S. Krajjak and P. Tuwanut, "A survey on internet of things architecture, protocols, possible applications, security, privacy, real-world implementation and future trends," *2015 IEEE 16th International Conference on Communication Technology (ICCT)*, 2015, pp. 26-31, doi: 10.1109/ICCT.2015.7399787.
- [11] H. M. Kadhim and A. A. Oglah, "Congestion Avoidance and Control in Internet Router Based on Fuzzy AQM," *Engineering and Technology Journal*, vol. 39, no. 2A, pp. 233-247, 2021, doi: 10.30684/etj.v39i2A.1799.
- [12] H. A. Abdulmohsin, "Design and Implementation a Server Receiving Data in Both Forms TCP and UDP Through the Same Port and its Impact on the Network Performance," *Engineering and Technology Journal*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 317-327, 2016. [Online]. Available: https://etj.uotechnology.edu.iq/article_112664.html
- [13] S. G. Langer, T. French, and C. Segovis, "TCP/IP optimization over wide area networks: implications for teleradiology," *Journal of Digital Imaging*, vol. 24, pp. 314-321, 2011, doi: 10.1007/s10278-010-9309-2.
- [14] S. N. Abdullah, B. A. Jumaa, and O. A. Mohamad, "Effect of Using Header Compression Method in TCP/IP Protocol Over HDLC in SCADA System," *Engineering and Technology Journal*, vol. 27, no. 15, pp. 2806-2813, 2009. [Online]. Available: https://etj.uotechnology.edu.iq/article_43184.html
- [15] T. Yoshino, Y. Sugawara, K. Inagami, J. Tamatsukuri, M. Inaba, and K. Hiraki, "Performance optimization of TCP/IP over 10 gigabit ethernet by precise instrumentation," in *SC'08: Proceedings of the 2008 ACM/IEEE Conference on Supercomputing*, 2008,

- pp. 1-12, doi: 10.1109/sc.2008.5215913.
- [16] G. Di Fatta, F. Hoffmann, G. Lo Re, and A. Urso, "A genetic algorithm for the design of a fuzzy controller for active queue management," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C (Applications and Reviews)*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 313-324, 2003, doi: 10.1109/TSMCC.2003.818946.
- [17] A. K. A. Hassan and S. S. Jasim, "Integrating neural network with genetic algorithms for the classification plant disease," *Engineering and Technology Journal*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 686-701, 2010. [Online]. Available: https://etj.uotechnology.edu.iq/article_27082.html
- [18] R. De Oliveira and T. Braun, "A delay-based approach using fuzzy logic to improve TCP error detection in ad hoc networks," in *2004 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (IEEE Cat. No. 04TH8733)*, 2004, vol. 3, pp. 1666-1671, doi: 10.1109/WCNC.2004.1311803.
- [19] S. -C. Gan and H. Guo, "The research of PID self-tuning based on fuzzy genetic algorithm," in *2011 Eighth International Conference on Fuzzy Systems and Knowledge Discovery (FSKD)*, 2011, pp. 308-312, doi: 10.1109/FSKD.2011.6019590.
- [20] S. W. Shneen, A. Z. Salman, Q. A. Jawad, and H. Shareef, "Advanced optimal by PSO-PI for DC motor," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 165-175, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v16.i1.pp165-175.
- [21] T. M. Shami, A. A. El-Saleh, M. Alswaitti, Q. Al-Tashi, M. A. Summakieh, and S. Mirjalili, "Particle swarm optimization: A comprehensive survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3142859.
- [22] A. Dabiri, B. P. Moghaddam, J. A. T. Machado, "Optimal variable-order fractional PID controllers for dynamical systems," *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 339, pp. 40-48, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cam.2018.02.029.
- [23] C. Zhao and L. Guo, "PID controller design for second-order nonlinear uncertain systems," *Science China Information Sciences*, vol. 60, 2017, doi: 10.1007/s11432-016-0879-3.
- [24] M. Merai, M. W. Naouar, I. S. -Belkhdja, and E. Monmasson, "An adaptive PI controller design for DC-link voltage control of single-phase grid-connected converters," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 66, no. 8, pp. 6241-6249, 2019, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2018.2871796.
- [25] K. Ranjbaran and M. Tabatabaei, "Fractional order [PI],[PD] and [PI][PD] controller design using Bode's integrals," *International Journal of Dynamics and Control*, vol. 6, pp. 200-212, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s40435-016-0301-7.
- [26] S. Waley, C. Mao, and N. K. Bachache, "Biogeography based optimization for tuning FLC controller of PMSM," *International Conference in Swarm Intelligence*, 2015, pp. 395-402, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-20466-6_42.
- [27] K. Karthikeyan and P. Lakshmi, "Optimal design of PID controller for improving rotor angle stability using BBO," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 38, pp. 889-902, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.proeng.2012.06.112.
- [28] H. Ma and D. Simon, "Blended biogeography-based optimization for constrained optimization," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 517-525, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.engappai.2010.08.005.
- [29] M. Sheikhan, E. Hemmati, and R. Shahnaazi, "GA-PSO-optimized neural-based control scheme for adaptive congestion control to improve performance in multimedia applications," *Majlesi Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1711/1711.06317.pdf>
- [30] S. S. Sabry and N. M. Kaittan, "Grey wolf optimizer based fuzzy-PI active queue management design for network congestion avoidance," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 199-208, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v18.i1.pp199-208.
- [31] M. Fajri and K. Ramli, "Optimizing PID TCP/AQM using nelder-mead simplex approach," in *Proc. of the 3rd International Conference on Communication and Information Processing*, 2017, pp. 292-295, doi: 10.1145/3162957.3163017.
- [32] Z. -H. Li, Y. Liu, and Y. -W. Jing, "Active queue management algorithm for TCP networks with integral backstepping and minimax," *International Journal of Control, Automation and Systems*, vol. 17, pp. 1059-1066, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s12555-018-0447-5.
- [33] K. Wang, Y. Liu, X. Liu, Y. Jing, and S. Zhang, "Adaptive fuzzy funnel congestion control for TCP/AQM network," *ISA Transactions*, vol. 95, pp. 11-17, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.isatra.2019.05.015.
- [34] D. Simon, "Biogeography-Based Optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 702-713, 2008, doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2008.919004.
- [35] N. Khanduja and B. Bhushan, "CSTR Control Using IMC-PID, PSO-PID, and Hybrid BBO-FF-PID Controller," *Applications of Artificial Intelligence Techniques in Engineering*, 2019, pp. 519-526, doi: 10.1007/978-981-13-1822-1_48.
- [36] S. W. Shneen, M. Q. Sulttan, and M. K. Oudah, "Design and implementation of a stability control system for TCP/AQM network," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 129-136, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v22.i1.pp129-136.
- [37] M. Q. Sulttan, M. H. Jaber, and S. W. Shneen, "Proportional-integral genetic algorithm controller for stability of TCP network," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6225-6232, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i6.pp6225-6232.
- [38] G. A. Aziz, M. H. Jaber, M. Q. Sulttan, and S. W. Shneen, "Simulation Model of Enhancing Performance of TCP/AQM Networks by Using Matlab," *Journal of Engineering & Technological Sciences*, vol. 54, no. 4, 2022, doi: 10.5614/j.eng.technol.sci.2022.54.4.4.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Manal Hadi Jaber she is a lecturer at the department of Electromechanical Engineering University of Technology-Iraq. She obtained Bachelor's degree in electrical engineering from University of Technology, Iraq, in 1998, and Master degree in electrical engineering from University of Technology, Iraq, in 2005. Her research areas are communications, electronics, and electrical engineering. She can be contacted at email: 50029@uotechnology.edu.iq.

Manal Kadhim Oudah received the B.Sc. degree in Educational Technology / electrical engineering from University of Technology, Iraq, in 1995, M.Sc. degree in Educational Technology / electrical engineering from University of Technology, Iraq, in 2002, and the Ph.D. in electrical engineering - communication and electronic from University of Technology, Iraq, in 2009. Her research areas are communication, electronics, and digital signal processing. She can be contacted at email: Manal.K.Oudah@uotechnology.edu.iq.

Mohammed Qasim Sulttan received his B.Sc. (Electrical Engineering & Education) and MSc (Engineering Educational Technology/Electrical Engineering) from University of Technology in 1996, 20005 respectively and PhD from Huazhong University of Science and Technology - China in (Information & Communication Engineering) During 2016. Work at Department of Electromechanical Engineering from 1998 to 2005 as an engineer and from 2005 until Know as a lecturer. Interested Filed: - His research areas are Electrical-Electronics Engineering, Communication and Information Engineering, MIMO Technics. He can be contacted at email: mohammed.q.mohammed@uotechnology.edu.iq.

Salam Waley Shneen Educational Background: July 2016 PhD, Degree in Electrical Engineering-Power Electronic, School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Huazhong University of Science and Technology (HUST). Nov 2005 MSc, Degree in Engineering Educational Technology-Electrical Engineering, Technical Education Department, University of Technology, Iraq-Baghdad. July 1998 BSc, Degree in Electrical Engineering and Education, Technical Education Department, University of Technology, Iraq-Baghdad. Oct 1994 Diploma in Electrical Technology, Technical Instructors Training Institute, Iraq Baghdad. 1992 High School Bakalaria Degree Preparatory Technical School (Electrical Section), Almashtal Technical Secondary School Iraq-Baghdad. Work Experience 1998-2005 Engineer in: Electronic Lab., Digital Electronic Lab., Communication Lap., Fundamental of Electric Engineering Lab. Cad Lab. In Technical Education Department, University of Technology, Iraq-Baghdad. 2005-2016 Assistant Lecturer in: Electronic Lab., Lecturer Advanced Electronic, Lecturer Fundamental of Electric Engineering, Technical Education Department, Electromechanical Department University of Technology, Iraq-Baghdad. 2016-2017 Lecturer in: Electronic Lab. Fundamental of Electric Engineering Lab., Lecturer Electronic Circuits, Lecturer Fundamental of Electric Engineering with Electrical and Electronic Circuits Electromechanical Department University of Technology, Iraq-Baghdad. 2017-10Apr.2022 Lecturer in: Energy and Renewable Energies Technology Center, University of Technology, Iraq-Baghdad. 10Apr.2022- today Lecturer in: Nanotechnology and advanced material research Center, University of Technology, Iraq-Baghdad. He can be contacted at email: salam.w.shneen@uotechnology.edu.iq.